

Why Electronic Open Access Matters. Analysis of Publications on Energy Topics

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Annotation

The paper analyzes the possible reasons why the growth of the number of publications in the journal *Energies* for 2011-2020 is more than 10 times higher than the number of publications in *Applied Energy* or *Energy* with the best citation rates and published by one of the oldest publishers - Elsevier.

It is shown that the significant growth in the number of publications of *Energies* can be explained by the following features of the journal. The journal with open access to all full-text articles is published only in electronic format, while only 4.6% of publications of the journal *Energy* and 12.1% of publications of the journal *Applied Energy* are open access, these journals have printed versions. The journal *Energies* admits articles of large length, such as 66 pages per publication. Its publication fees are substantially less than those of journals of a similar subject but with print versions, ~\$2224 for *Energies*, \$3400 for *Energy*, and \$3400 for *Applied Energy*, respectively. The rate of publication of articles is several times faster than that of Elsevier journals. The first decision is made in about 16.5 days from the time the article is submitted; acceptance for publication is in 3.5 days. The journal has developed a large community of reviewers and affiliated institutions who are rewarded for their work with reduced fees for journal publications. The journal is less dominated by authors from China and the United States, making it more attractive to authors from other countries. The Lens platform classifies all articles in *Energies* as belonging to the General Computer Science Subject, which is especially important for finding optimal solutions to various energy problems, while the *Energy* and

Applied Energy journals categorize their publications into more traditional Subjects: General Energy; Pollution; Building and Construction; Civil and Structural Engineering.

Keywords: electronic journal, open access, energy, bibliometric analysis, the Lens platform.

Introduction

The debate on Open Access (OA) to scholarly publications concerns economic, technological, political, ethical, and legal aspects of publishing. In theory, one can find arguments explaining the benefits of OA publications: increased accessibility, easier search, wider audience, faster publication, easier collaboration, but these arguments need concrete confirmation.

The following publications discuss important issues related to Open Access.

In [1] the authors analyzed 18.3 million articles and reviews for the period 2005–2015. They found that the proportion of OA publications was 5% lower in WoS than in Scopus, and that OA journals only increased the number of publications, but not the number of citations.

In [2] it was found that publishing OA journals in collaboration with major publishers increases the number of citations to articles, and that the effect for journals in non-English-speaking countries is more significant than for journals in English-speaking countries. Publishers also benefit from the collaboration; they can strengthen their position in the OA journal market. The SJR and SNIP of most journals have increased after cooperating with major publishers.

In the paper [3], the authors tested the hypothesis that journals with a high impact factor (IF) have higher article processing fees (APC). The results show a positive relationship between APC and journals with a high IF value, and significant differences in APC between the analyzed fields of study.

[4] This study analyzed the strategies for APC of journals by BMC (formerly BioMed Central) and Hindawi between 2018 and 2020. BMC raised the APCs for 89 journals (72.4%), and Hindawi raised APCs for 96 journals (88.9%) in 2019. The 62 of the 89

BMC journals further raised the APCs in 2020, the APCs for 59 of the 96 Hindawi journals declined in the same year.

To gain insight into the status and scientific potential of European full open access journals (OAJ), the authors [5] used the following bibliometric indicators: quartiles and SJR (SCImago Journal Rank) for the period 2012-2015 and the Hirsch index for 2015 to choose the journals for analysis.

Of all the OAJs in the Scopus database, 41% are published in European countries. The journals in the sample are predominantly published by countries that are leaders in R&D and innovation. The share of European OAJs exceeds 70%.

As of this writing (February 2021), the situation with OA publications in the leading abstract databases is as follows:

Web of Science Core Collection: results: 51,475 for the query: TOPIC ("Open Access") AND Timespan: 2011-2020, Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, ESCI and 2,399 results if TITLE: ("Open Access").

These results show an interest in the OA topic for authors: 105 publications in 2011 and 337 in 2020 from all 2399 results.

The interest of WoS journals in open publications can be seen by the query: TITLE: (energy*) for the same other restrictions – 258,533 all publications, Open Access – 75,065 (29%).

Scopus data: 3,849 results for TITLE ("Open Access") in 2011-2020 and 1,983 are Open Access. For query: TITLE (energ*) AND PUBYEAR > 2010, 435,362 – all results and 129,430 (29.7%) for Open Access.

The Lens data: the pseudo query = Title: "Open Access" AND Year Published = (2011- 2020) gives 23,247 scholarly works. If Title: "energ*" the result is 787,013 publications, of which 169,908 (21.5%) are OA with open access colour = (gold, green, bronze).

Looking at the number of articles published in Lens on energy topics, we get the following distribution by year of OA publications: 2011→7522; 2012→9097; 2013→10219; 2014→12092; 2015→14049; 2016→14983; 2017→18008; 2018→19321; 2019→22394; 2020→19573;

Objectives, Materials and Methods

The purpose of this paper was to identify possible reasons for the increase in the number of publications in an Open Access electronic journal – Energies of the MDPI publisher, which is in Q3/Q2 by WoS and Scopus, significantly exceeds the growth rate of the number of publications in Elsevier's Energy and Applied Energy journals, which are in Q1.

Bibliometric materials for articles in Energy, Energy and Applied Energy journals were obtained from the Lens – an open global cyberinfrastructure for data and analytics for both patents and scholarly works.¹

The Lens has certain advantages over WoS and Scopus: open access without subscription, one-time download of bibliometric data up to 50,000 records, advanced open access querying and analytics, categorization of records by fields of study, and a large database, which at the time of writing was 127,471,322 patent records and 225,109,652 research papers.

The basic data for the analysis: 15,259 bibliometric records for the journal Energies and 12,670 for the journals Energy and Applied Energy.

Methods. Queries to the Lens were built using filters: Year Published, Source Title, Publication Type, Publisher, Open Access Colour.

Most of the data for tables and graphs of our article are obtained using the Lens platform Analytics section.

VOSviewer version 1.6.16 – a software tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks, was used to determine clusters of co-occurrences of Field of Study categories for records of Energies, Energy and Applied Energy journals [6].

A general note, in this article the terms used by the Lens platform are given in their original form in order to distinguish them from the general text, e.g., Fields of Study, Subject, Document Count, Average Scholar Citations, Scholarly Works and so on.

Results

¹ <https://www.lens.org/> – Lens serves global patent and scholarly knowledge as a public good to inform science and technology enabled problem-solving.

Таблица 1. Общая информация о журналах по состоянию на 01 февраля 2021 г., по Sciemago Journal Rank Scopus and the Journal Citation Reports WoS

Table 1. General information about journals on Feb 01, 2021 as in Sciemago Journal Rank by Scopus and the Journal Citation Reports by WoS

Journal*	H Index	Subject Area by Scopus, SJR, Quartile	Category by JCR, Impact Factor, Quartile	Publications growth**
Applied Energy	189	Energy, Engineering, Environmental Science; 3.607, Q1	Energy & Fuels, Engineering, Chemical; 8.848, Q1	3.05
Energy	173	Energy, Engineering, Environmental Science, Mathematics; 2.166, Q1	Energy & Fuels, Thermodynamics; 6.082, Q1	3.1
Energies	78	Energy, Engineering, Environmental Science, Mathematics; 0.635, Q2	Energy & Fuels; 2.702, Q3	35.8

*Applied Energy and Energy are published by Elsevier, Energies – by MDPI.

** The increase in the number of Energies publications for 2011-2020 is more than 10 times higher than of Applied Energy or Energy.

The number of articles for years 2011–2020 (The Lens database as Feb 01, 2021):

Applied Energy: 579→765→979→1300→1245→1670→2430→1851→1838→1765

Energy: 762→830→870→1306→1462→1666→2448→2244→2427→2356

Energies: 189→433→487→642→972→1109→2219→3620→4870→6766

The overall increase in publication activity for all journals of the Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI) was 30.1 times, 5223 articles in 2011, 157401 in 2020. Thus, rapid growth is consistent with all of MDPI's business.

Elsevier BV published 376476 articles in 2011 and 555694 in 2020; total growth of all publications was 1.5 times. The energy topic is growing faster than the general trend – 2.17 (166468/76562).

Thus, journals Energy and Applied Energy have higher indexes based on the citation of articles, they are published by one of the oldest and strongest publishing houses in the world, but in some ways, MDPI journals have become very popular with authors, and this deserves a more detailed analysis.

Comparison of other characteristics of the journals

All publications of MDPI are Open Access and in electronic form.

Energy: 4.6% and Applied Energy: 12.1% publications are Open Access.

Таблица. 2. Energy, количество опубликованных статей по годам

Table 2. Energy, number of articles published by year²

Year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Open Access	30	68	56	58	117
All	1535	1994	2352	2116	2537

Таблица. 3. Applied Energy, количество опубликованных статей по годам

Table 3. Applied Energy, number of articles published by year³

Year	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Open Access	87	101	137	109	173
All	1603	1497	1654	1640	1430

In both cases, a significant increase in the share of Open Access publications was observed in 2020.

Таблица. 4. Средние характеристики публикаций в журналах издательства MDPI (Energies) и Elsevier (Applied Energy+ Energy)

Table 4. Average characteristics of publications in MDPI (Energies) and Elsevier (Applied Energy+ Energy) journals

² <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy>

³ <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy>

publisher	authors per article	References in the article	pages per article	citation	articles without citations, %
Elsevier	4.4	41.9	12.6	10.4	15
MDPI	4.27	31.58	19.2	3.5	34

Articles in Elsevier have higher citations, but the average number of pages is higher in the MDPI journal.

Examples of Energies articles with high page counts of 66, 52, and 49, respectively [7–8]

The price of publication also matters:

Energy – an article publishing charge: \$3400

Applied Energy – \$4020

Energies – 2000 CHF (~\$2224)

Paper versions may require a separate printing fee for color illustrations.

The advantages of electronic publications in terms of speed of publishing should be taken into account. Citing the Energies journal website:⁴

“Rapid Publication: manuscripts are peer-reviewed and a first decision provided to authors approximately 16.5 days after submission; acceptance to publication is undertaken in 3.5 days (median values for papers published in this journal in the second half of 2020)”.

With this in mind, other publishers began releasing articles online earlier than paper versions.

To facilitate rapid open scholarly exchange, according to MDPI, more than 84,200 academic editors support MDPI's 314 peer-reviewed journals.

An increasing number of journals are publishing articles online before they are officially included in a planned volume/issue; this is often referred to as "Early Access".

A printed version of the journal not only makes the publication process more expensive but also requires additional time, which is negatively perceived by authors

⁴ <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies> – Energies (ISSN 1996-1073; CODEN: ENERGA) is a peer-reviewed, open access journal

who want to publish their work as quickly as possible. So, the WoS platform, which is very careful in its actions, is forced to take this into account.

Given the trends toward open electronic publishing, Journal Citation Reports published by Web of Science starting in 2021 will incorporate Early Access content and provide metrics – including the Journal Impact Factor™ (JIF) ⁵.

Energies journal has some business advantages that are rarely met in other publishers:

- the Institutions and their members affiliated with Energies receive a discount on the article processing charges.
- reviewers who submit timely and detailed peer-review reports receive vouchers entitling them to an APC discount on their next publication in any MDPI journal in recognition of the work done.

The number of publications per year matters because it not only reduces publication time, but it also increases the overall citation of the journal and keeps readers' attention – they browse the journal regularly and it becomes part of their routine.

MDPI publisher has 70 journals with total number of articles more than 1000 per year and 20 – more than 5000. Energies published 6766 articles in 2020.

The next important step in comparing journals is the subject of publications.

The relevance of the subject matter for the interest in the journal. More research is being done on hot topics, so more articles are appearing.

To study the topics of articles in the journals Energies, Energy and Applied Energy bibliometric data of the Lens platform was used. The Lens categorizes records by field of study, provides a one-time download of a large number of bibliometric data and extended open access to analytics.

The Lens data analysis, main remarks

The dominant Fields of Study in the journal publications were considered in the three cases:

1. Fields of Study with the highest number of articles published in the journal in 2018-2020 (Top Field of Study by Document Count – by the Lens terminology)

⁵ <https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/article/the-jcr-reload-and-a-look-ahead-to-the-introduction-of-early-access-content-in-2021/> – The JCR Reload and a look ahead to the introduction of early access content in 2021

2. Fields of Study with the largest number of articles with the most average citation by scientific papers (Top Field of Study ordered by Document Count by Average Scholar Citations – as in the Lens)
3. Fields of Study ordered by Average Scholar Citations with the most average citation by scientific papers (Top Field of Study ordered by Average Scholar Citations by Average Scholar Citations – as in the Lens)
4. Fields of Study ordered by Average Patent Citations with the most average citation by scientific papers (Top Field of Study ordered by Average Patent Citations by Average Patent Citations – as in the Lens)

Case 2 example as in form of the Lens Analysis tab: Facet=Field of Study; Limit=20; Order by=Document Count; Metric=Scholarly Citations; Aggregation=Average;

The Order By parameter determines the criterion by which the data is sorted, then N Field of Study records are selected from them according to the Limit number, this forms a sample within which the citation rate (average or total, by Scholarly Citations or Patent Citations) of articles related to a particular f Field of Study is evaluated.

Therefore, the result depends on both the Limit value and the sort parameter.

For example, we took 20 Fields of Study with the largest number of articles and determine how the Fields of Study are ranked by the average citation of related articles from scientific papers, but if we took N=1000, we will get a different ranking of Fields of Study.

Thus, the analytics of the Lens platform allows getting different slices of estimates of the importance of the Field of Study, for example, in terms of the total number of articles, in terms of citations from scientific papers or patents.

Field of Study analysis for Energies journal

The data for analysis were obtained on request: Year Published = (2018-2020), Source Title = (Energies), valid as of January 29, 2021, which returned 15,259 Scholarly Works as a result.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of Fields of Study by the number of articles assigned to a given Field of Study by the Lens platform.

Рис. 1. Распределение основных областей исследований (Field of Study) по количеству документов согласно анализу платформы the Lens

Fig. 1. Top Field of Study by Document Count according to the Lens analysis

The simple aggregation of the terms presented in Fig. 1 allows us to formulate at least 4 thematic clusters:

1. Computer science (5741); Control theory (1727); Automotive engineering (1132); Efficient energy use (745); Mathematical optimization (516); Artificial neural network (374); Algorithm (337); Computational fluid dynamics (313); Mathematics (307).
2. Environmental science (3016); Renewable energy (1636); Photovoltaic system (1011); Wind power (775); Environmental economics (721); Greenhouse gas (414); Biomass (407); Electric vehicle (357); Waste management (337).
3. Voltage (1088); Electric power system (957); Electricity (863); Grid (699); Electricity generation (645); Energy storage (603); Turbine (587); Battery (electricity) (560); Electrical engineering (528); Distributed generation (423); Microgrid (401); Electric vehicle (357); Smart grid (356); AC power (319); Electronic engineering (317).
4. Materials science (2797); Composite material (404).

The data obtained above allow us to formulate an example of relevance storytelling: computational and materials science for development of advanced electric grid systems for renewable energy and ecology.

If we take the 20 fields with the highest number of publications and consider how they are ranked by being cited, we get the results presented in fig. 2.

Рис. 2. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по количеству работ, относящихся к ним, по среднему количеству цитирований их в научных работах согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens

Fig. 2. Top 20 Field of Study ordered by Document Count by Average Scholar Citations according to the Lens analysis

In this distribution, Fields of Study that are general in nature, such as Computer science, Environment science, occur less frequently than those in fig. 1 than Fields of Study that are more specific, for example, Efficient energy use, Photovoltaic system, Energy consumption.

If we take a large number of Fields of Study, for example, 1000, then narrower topics may have a higher citation, thus it is possible to show that the topic has potential for development, but this is only one of the criteria, a good option is to consider the

relationship with other developed fields of knowledge and the trend of increasing interest in the topic.

The list of the most cited fields for N=1000 is as follows: Biochemical engineering (9.5); Big data (9.3); Industrial engineering (8.8); Electrical load (8.1); Deep learning (8.1); Multiple-criteria decision analysis (8.05); Recurrent neural network (8.05); Load forecasting (7.95); Metaheuristic (7.9); Hydrothermal carbonization (7.6).

Biochemical engineering is associated not only with biofuels, but also with the development of engineering solutions for affordable nutrition.

If we compare it with the data presented in Figure 1, the topics of computer science and mathematics are also heavily represented here, but reflected in more specific terms: Big data; Deep learning; Multiple-criteria decision analysis; Recurrent neural network; Load forecasting.

Using the Fields of Study with the highest average citation and constructing their distribution according to the average citation we rely on a sample of articles with a high citation rate. The results of this distribution for the 20 most average cited Fields of Study are shown in fig. 3.

Рис. 3. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по средней цитируемости работ, относящихся к ним, по

среднему количеству цитирований научными работами согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens

Fig. 3. Top 20 Field of Study by Average Scholar Citations Order by Average Scholar Citations

A comparison of Figures 2 and 3 shows that in the third case the Fields of Study with a higher average citation are selected, but there are fewer articles on these fields, as can be seen from the comparison with fig.1

The average citation of the Field of Study can be estimated not only by the scientific papers' citation but also by the citation of articles related to a given Field of Study by patents

Рис. 4. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по средней цитируемости работ, относящихся к ним, по среднему количеству цитирований патентами согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens.

Fig. 4. Top 20 Field of Study by Average Patent Citations Order by Average Patent Citations

Citation articles related to a particular Field of Study by patents is more reflective of applied industry interests than citation by research papers, which are more in the interest of basic research.

For example, the Stirling engine⁶ is more attractive for engineering implementations than for scientific research.

Correlation, Decision tree – also more about their implementation, but can be classified as Computer science Field of Study.

Computer science and control theory are closely connected clusters. Environment science is near renewable energy.

Field of Study analysis for Energy and Applied Energy journals

The data for analysis were obtained on request: Year Published = (2018-2020), Source Title = (Energy AND Applied Energy), valid as of January 29, 2021, which returned 12,670 Scholarly Works as result.

Fig. 5 shows the distribution of Fields of Study by the number of articles assigned to a given Field of Study.

Рис. 5. Распределение основных областей исследований (Field of Study) по количеству документов согласно анализу платформы the Lens

Fig. 5. Top Field of Study by Document Count according to the Lens analysis

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stirling_engine

In these journals, Environmental science rank first, but computer science and materials science are also well represented. In addition, Renewable energy and Environmental economy contribute to solving Environmental science issues. These journals focus more on engineering tasks: Process engineering, Automotive engineering, Chemical engineering, Nuclear engineering, compared to Energies journal.

Рис. 6. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по количеству работ, относящихся к ним, по среднему количеству цитирований их в научных работах согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens.

Fig. 6. Top 20 Field of Study ordered by Document Count by Average Scholar Citations according to the Lens analysis

Mathematical optimization issues, especially those related to Photovoltaic system, Energy storage, Renewable energy, Electric power system, Electricity generation, Environmental economics and Energy consumption are the most cited in this sample. Efficient energy use on Fig.2. and Mathematical optimization on Fig.2-2. – go well together in terms of meaning.

Рис. 7. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по средней цитируемости работ, относящихся к ним, по среднему количеству цитирований научными работами согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens.

Fig. 7. Top 20 Field of Study by Average Scholar Citations Order by Average Scholar Citations

Information system, Moving bed [10], Commerce, Architecture model, Cape Verde [11] – this list of terms may seem inconsistent in the context of energy topics, but more detailed study of the publications containing these terms disproves this assertion.

In [10] authors propose to investigate gravity-driven granular flow in the moving bed (подвижный слой) heat exchanger with tube oscillation by discrete element method (DEM).

Prediction of solar irradiance is essential for electrical power grids with distributed solar photovoltaic generations and authors do so by using long short-term memory (LSTM) networks for the dataset collected on the island of Santiago, Cape Verde [11].

Рис. 8. Распределение 20 основных направлений исследований, отсортированных по средней цитируемости работ, относящихся к ним, по среднему количеству цитирований патентами согласно данным анализа платформы the Lens

Fig. 8. Top 20 Field of Study by Average Patent Citations Order by Average Patent Citations

Perovskite, ceramics with perovskite structure – are very relevant topics, for example, for photovoltaic cells ⁷ so articles on this topic can often be cited by patents.

Таблица 5. Распределение по годам общего числа публикаций и публикаций, относящихся к 3 ведущим темам в журнале Energies

Table 5. Distribution by year of the total number of publications and publications related to the 3 leading topics in the Energies journal

FS/year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
all	189	433	487	642	972	1109	2219	3620	4870	6766
1	3	4	5	8	13	42	196	1563	1992	2395
2	16	24	27	31	48	59	120	629	971	1538
3	8	12	18	30	55	86	216	644	885	1348

⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/materials-science/perovskite-solar-cell> – Perovskite Solar Cell

FS/year → Field of Study per year.

1 → Computer science; 2 → Environmental science, 3 → Materials science.

число публикаций по всем трем доминирующим темам резко возрастает начиная с 2018 года, при этом общее число публикаций растет более плавно.

Таблица 6. Распределение по годам общего числа публикаций и публикаций, относящихся к 3 ведущим темам в журналах Energy and Applied Energy

Table 6. Distribution by year of the total number of publications and publications related to the 3 leading topics in Energy and Applied Energy journals

FS/year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
All	1341	1595	1849	2606	2707	3336	4878	4095	4265	4121
1	589	755	881	1183	1264	1632	1769	247	6	8
2	125	135	151	193	187	217	194	1107	1326	1258
3	114	137	201	286	315	347	324	902	1084	966

FS/year → Field of Study per year.

1 → Engineering – the number of publications on the topic declines after 2017, 2 → Environmental science, 3 → Materials science. – the number of publications on the topic increases sharply after 2017, but less heavily than in the Energies' publications

The main conclusion on this section: there is no fundamental difference in the subject of the two publications, the primary goal can be formulated as optimization of the energy transition. The individual issues of the new energy are sufficiently well-developed, it is important to achieve the synergy of the achieved results.

The subject of the Energies journal shows a higher affinity to computer sciences, and Energy and Apply Energy to environmental sciences. Moreover, the Lens system classifies all the articles in the Energies journal into the General Computer Science Subject, and journals Energy and Apply Energy to the following Subjects: General Energy; Pollution; Building and Construction; Civil and Structural Engineering.

Comparison of the publication activity of authors whose institutions are affiliated with different countries

Таблица 7. Страны, институты которых имеют наибольшее число публикаций в журналах Energies и Energy + Apply Energy

Table. 7. Countries whose institutions have the highest number of publications in Energies and Energy + Apply Energy journals

Energies			Energy and Apply Energy		
Countries	records	% of 15102	Countries	records	% of 12287
Peoples R China	4674	30.95	Peoples R China	5160	41.996
South Korea	1377	9.118	Usa	1664	13.543
Poland	1182	7.827	England	957	7.789
Italy	1128	7.469	Italy	621	5.054
Usa	1102	7.297	Iran	581	4.729
Spain	1000	6.622	Germany	546	4.444
Germany	707	4.681	Spain	490	3.988
England	698	4.622	South Korea	465	3.784
Australia	457	3.026	Australia	462	3.76
Japan	410	2.715	Canada	442	3.597

Note. The data in the Tab. 7 are taken from the Scopus database, because the data of the Lens platform showed inconsistency between the data for individual countries and the total amount of data for the Energies journal.

The Lens platform does not export the affiliation field, this data is only available in the "Analysis" section, which makes it difficult to diagnose the cause of data inconsistency.

In Energies, the number of publications is more balanced across the countries. Publications from China (42%) and the United States (13.5%) are dominated in Energy and Apply Energy journals. Perhaps the MDPI publishing has more growth potential precisely because of the diversity of countries that post their articles.

Заклучение

The fact that the increase in the number of Energies publications over 2011-2020 is more than 10 times higher than the number of Applied Energy or Energy publications can be supposedly explained by the following results of the analysis presented in this article:

1. Energies is an Open Access electronic journal. Only 4.6% of Energy and 12.1% of Applied Energy publications are Open Access, these journals have print versions.

2. Articles in Energy and Applied Energy have higher citations, but the average number of pages is higher in the Energies journal. Some articles have more than 50 pages.
 3. An article publishing charge for Energy is \$3400, for Applied Energy – \$4020 and Energies – 2000 CHF (~\$2224)
 4. Energies average first decision provided to authors is approximately 16.5 days after submission; acceptance to publication is undertaken in 3.5 days. The author could not find official statistics for Energy and Applied Energy but it typically takes 5-10 months from the day the article is submitted until it appears online.
 5. Energies journal has some business advantages that are rarely met in other publishers:
 - the Institutions and their members affiliated with Energies receive a discount on the article processing charges.
 - reviewers who submit timely and detailed peer-review reports receive vouchers entitling them to an APC discount on their next publication in any MDPI journal in recognition of the work done.
 6. The journal is less dominated by authors from China and the United States.
 7. The topics of the Energies journal show a higher affinity to computer sciences, and Energy and Apply Energy to environmental sciences. Moreover, the Lens system classifies all of the articles in the Energies journal into the General Computer Science Subject, and journals Energy and Apply Energy to the following Subjects: General Energy; Pollution; Building and Construction; Civil and Structural Engineering.
- A more detailed examination of energy topics shows that the major trend in research can be formulated as the optimization of the energy transition, so the articles of the journal energy seem more relevant.

P.S. It is likely that the MDPI has created an effective platform for interaction between publication authors and reviewers. By making the business of authors and reviewers productive by quickly passing a large number of articles through the platform, including a substantial amount of rejected publications, MDPI has made its business efficient as well

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